

D7.1

Strategy for dissemination, exploitation and communication

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Funded by
the European Union

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D7.1

Strategy for dissemination, exploitation and communication

DELIVERABLE TYPE

Report

MONTH AND DATE OF DELIVERY

M6 ----, 28/02/2023

WORK PACKAGE

WP 7

LEADER

APRE

DISSEMINATION LEVEL

Public

AUTHORS

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Programme

HORIZON
EUROPE

Grant agreement

101060588

Start

Sept.2022

Duration

36 Months

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Revision History

VERSION	DATE	REVIEWER	MODIFICATIONS
0.1	08/02/2023	Lorenzo Giannetti	Structure of the deliverable: objectives, targets, tools and channels, communication kit, introduction
0.2	13/02/2023	Serena Fabbrini Lorenzo Giannetti	KIPs, monitoring, timeplan, conclusions
0.3	17/02/2023	Serena Fabbrini Lorenzo Giannetti	Review and share with the Coordinator
0.4	21/02/2023	Luana Ladu	Comments
0.5	22/02/2023	Serena Fabbrini Enrica Imbert Nikola Matovic	Editing, new structure. UNIT provided inputs for the Exploitation strategy
0.6	27/02/2023	Serena Fabbrini	Editing and inputs
0.7	28/02/2023	Enrica Imbert Serena Fabbrini	Inputs provided Final version shared with the Coordinator for the submission
0.8.1	4/07/2024	Valeria Mingardi	Integration of feedback after review meeting. Specifically: updated executive summary, updated table 3,4,5,9, added § 7.1, explanation

			of monitoring tools in 7.2, and updated §10.
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Partners short names

TUB	(Technische Universität Berlin)
UNITELMA	(Università degli studi Unitelma di Roma)
UNI	(Ente Italiano di Normazione)
AUA	(Geoniko Panepistimion Athinon)
USC	(Universidad de Santiago de Compostela)
APRE	(Agenzia per la promozione della Ricerca Europea)
NOVA	(Nova - Institut für politische und Ökologische Innovation GMBH)
BAM	(Bundesanstalt für Materialforschung und Prüfung)
RSB	(Roundtable on Sustainable Biomaterials Association)
ISEAL	(ISEAL Alliance)

Abbreviations

SCS	Sustainability Certification Schemes
EU	European Union
EC	European Commission
B2B	Business-to-business
GA	Grant Agreement
M	Month
D	Deliverable
T	Task
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
TBD	To be determined
TG	Target
SMA	Social media accounts
SNs	Social Networks
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
EuBioNet	European Bioeconomy Network
CoDNOC	Communication, Dissemination, Networking and Outreach Coordinator
CSL	Certification schemes and labels
DMP	Data Management Plan

Executive summary

This document defines the strategy that will guide the dissemination and communication efforts of STAR4BBS Consortium throughout the duration of the project.

Aims and scope of dissemination, communication and exploitation are different, according to the official glossary of the EC¹:

1. **Dissemination:** the public disclosure of the results (e.g. any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected) by appropriate means, other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results, including by scientific publications in any medium
2. **Exploitation:** the use of results in further research and innovation activities other than those covered by the action concerned, including among other things, commercial exploitation such as developing, creating, manufacturing and marketing a product or process, creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities
3. **Communication:** these measures should promote the project throughout the full lifespan of the project. The aim is to inform, reach out to society and show the activities performed, and the use and benefits the project will have for citizens.

Dissemination, communication and exploitation Strategy has been developed during the first months of the project and it is integrated under WP7 – Communication, dissemination and international cooperation. Moreover, modifications were added after the first project review meeting in order to update the Strategy in terms of expected KPIs, monitoring and evaluation of communication and dissemination activities, and easily find the open access STAR4BBS publications.

APRE's team, as WP7 leader, will be responsible for the overall management and support of the activities defined under the present Dissemination, communication and exploitation Strategy and will develop the main tools and materials to be used during the project. The present document outlines:

- Objectives of the strategy;
- Target audiences and respective dissemination and communication objectives;
- STAR4BBS brand identity and Communication Kit;
- Main dissemination and communication tools and channels to reach the audiences;
- Main activities including an indicative timeline for their implementation;
- A set of Key Performance Indicators (KPI), barriers and obstacles considered to reach KPIs;
- Explanation of the monitoring and evaluation processes through KPIs, that allows the evaluation of the impact of communication and dissemination activities.

¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/support/glossary>

All partners will also be actively involved in the dissemination and communication actions implementation and are highly committed to ensure a satisfactory dissemination of the project's results. The expected contributions from partners are to:

- Implement promotional and dissemination campaigns in their own countries and at European level;
- Exploit their contacts and networks;
- Supply news and updates for the web portal and newsletter;
- Interact with the project's posts on various Social Media Channels;
- Participate in relevant events to promote the project and its outcomes.

1 Introduction

STAR4BBS is a three-year multidisciplinary and multi-actor collaborative project with the aim of maximizing the potential of Sustainability Certification Schemes (SCS) and labels to support a successful transition to sustainable bio-based economy. At the core of the STAR4BBS is the development of indicators and a new monitoring system for assessing the effectiveness and robustness of existing international and EU SCS, B2B labels, and related traceability systems applicable to biological feedstock and bio-based materials and products. STAR4BBS includes eight specific objectives:

1. gain a precise picture of existing international and EU SCS and labels both for biological feedstocks and biobased materials and products, as well existing monitoring systems;
2. gather specific global trade data and information on volumes of biological feedstock and bio-based materials and products, differentiating between certified and uncertified flows;
3. explore the impact and contribution of existing SCS and labels to enabling sustainability and also the impact on the adoption of SCS and labels on market access and trade within bio-based systems, and to what extent sustainability SCS and labels are a catalyst or barrier;
4. identify relevant and feasible indicators, related metrics and minimum sustainability and traceability requirements for inclusion in the monitoring system;
5. develop a fit-for-purpose monitoring system to assess the effectiveness and robustness of existing SCS and labels in supporting achievement of sustainability targets and enabling transparent traceability in global trade flows;
6. assess the effectiveness and robustness of reviewed SCS and labels by applying the monitoring system;
7. evaluate overall costs and benefits from adopting the reviewed SCS and labels in selected value chains and performing a feasibility study on B2B labels best-performing from either environmental or social aspects;
8. maximize both the relevance and the uptake of the project findings and recommendations involving a broad range of stakeholders.

The project involves important stakeholders² (scheme and labels owners, policy makers, industry, academia) in the design and development of the monitoring system and in the elaboration of practical recommendations emerging from the research and analysis, in order to ensure that the project achieves its goal.

To ensure that results gained during the course of the STAR4BBS project exert their full impact, effective activities for the dissemination, communication and exploitation of results will be pursued throughout the project duration. Thus, this Strategy underlines the overarching dissemination, communication and exploitation objectives of STAR4BBS, describes measures, timeframes and responsibilities of the partners during the lifetime of the project and defines the monitoring phases as well as the reporting of the project's achievements.

² For more detailed information about the involvement of stakeholders, please refer to STA4RBSS, D6.1 *STAR4BBS stakeholder map*.

2 Objectives of the Strategy

The main objective of the dissemination and communication strategy of the STAR4BBS project is to offer partners a set of guidelines, responsibilities and timelines on how/when/where to disseminate the project, as well as to encourage them to use their channels (corporate websites, social networks, etc.) to support the dissemination, with the following goals:

- Raise awareness on the project activities and events;
- Communicate and disseminate results achieved among STAR4BBS target groups;
- Identify and use the right channels to efficiently communicate with the target groups and stakeholders (including the identification of events, social media networks, press releases, multiplier organisations, etc.);
- Produce the necessary supporting material to ensure an effective dissemination, including printed material (i.e. brochure, poster, roll-up) and digital materials (videos, infographics);
- Facilitate regular communication, through press releases and newsletters, to inform about the latest news and developments of the project to the media;
- Identify potential ways for ensuring the use of the monitoring system beyond the duration of the project.

3 The strategy

The strategy focuses on establishing realistic dissemination and communication activities in line with the progress of the project and the utilization of appropriate tools, channels and formats to communicate with the target audiences in a defined timeline.

To achieve dissemination and communication objectives in a timely and adequate manner, STAR4BBS consortium will follow the roadmap shown in the Table 1 below.

Table 1 STAR4BBS communication and dissemination roadmap

Activity	Timeline	Description
Planning	M1-M6	Identify the communication and dissemination strategy to ensure a wide outreach of project's outcomes
Implementation	M6-M36	Produce a set of tools (supports and channels) to diffuse key messages extracted from the project results to the identified target groups
Monitoring	M6-M36	Analyse and assess the impact and success of dissemination and communication activities by comparing the results to the pre-established key performance indicators (KPIs)
Sustainability	M32-M36	Identify and establish mechanisms needed to ensure persistent and long-lasting visibility of STAR4BBS outcomes

3.1 Target groups

All communication messages will be tailored on the needs of the target audience. Since the beginning of the project, seven main target groups were identified:

1. Standards setting, labelling and certification organisations (even certification bodies);
2. Academia, research institutions and researchers;
3. Value chains actors (feedstocks producers, processors and industry bodies);
4. EU Policymakers;
5. Intergovernmental organizations (e.g. FAO);
6. Civil society (end-consumers organizations);
7. EU funded projects on the same topic

The following Table 2 indicates the objectives of the communication and dissemination activities for each selected category of the stakeholders. It also describes how different stakeholder groups will be approached.

Table 2 Target audience and dissemination and communication objectives

Target group	Dissemination objectives	Communication objectives
Standards setting, labelling and certification organisations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote STAR4BBS results and outputs Engage them in STAR4BBS workshops key-note speakers Engage them as Advisory Board members Promote recommendations Expand STAR4BBS database (newsletter) Promote co-creation workshops Engage them with social media activities to increase posts' engagement and overall followers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Receive feedback on recommendations Receive feedback on co-creation activities: what worked and what did not work, to improve future workshops Encourage interaction via social media to stimulate interest in the bioeconomy matter
Academia, research institutions and researchers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote STAR4BBS results and outputs Engage them in STAR4BBS workshops key-note speakers Engage them as Advisory Board members Promote recommendations Expand STAR4BBS database (newsletter) Promote co-creation workshops Engage them with social media activities to increase posts' engagement and overall followers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Receive feedback on recommendations Receive feedback on co-creation activities: what worked and what did not work, to improve future workshops Encourage interaction via social media to stimulate interest in the bioeconomy matter
Value chains actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote STAR4BBS results and outputs Engage them in STAR4BBS workshops key-note speakers Promote recommendations Expand STAR4BBS database (newsletter) Promote co-creation workshops 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Receive feedback on recommendations Receive feedback on co-creation activities: what worked and what did not work, to improve future workshops Encourage interaction via social media to stimulate interest in the bioeconomy matter
EU Policymakers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote STAR4BBS results and outputs Engage them in STAR4BBS workshops key-note speakers Promote recommendations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Receive feedback on recommendations Receive feedback on co-creation activities: what worked and what did not work, to improve future workshops

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expand STAR4BBS database (newsletter) • Promote co-creation workshops 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encourage interaction via social media to stimulate interest in the bioeconomy matter
Intergovernmental organizations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote STAR4BBS results and outputs • Engage them in STAR4BBS workshops key-note speakers • Engage them as Advisory Board members • Promote recommendations • Expand STAR4BBS database (newsletter) • Promote co-creation workshops <p>Engage them with social media activities to increase posts' engagement and overall followers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Receive feedback on recommendations • Receive feedback on co-creation activities: what worked and what did not work, to improve future workshops • Encourage interaction via social media to stimulate interest in the bioeconomy matter
Civil society	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engage them with social media activities to increase posts' engagement and overall followers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encourage interaction via social media to stimulate interest in the bioeconomy matter
EU funded projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expand STAR4BBS database (newsletter) • Promote STAR4BBS results and outputs • Engage them in STAR4BBS workshops key-note speakers • Promote recommendations • Expand STAR4BBS database (newsletter) • Promote co-creation workshops • Engage them with social media activities to increase posts' engagement and overall followers • Create new networking opportunities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Receive feedback on recommendations • Receive feedback on co-creation activities: what worked and what did not work, to improve future workshops • Encourage interaction via social media to stimulate interest in the bioeconomy matter • Encourage joint social campaigns

4 Brand identity

The visual identity of a project consists of a set of elements that forms its graphic individuality.

APRE developed an initial visual identity for the STAR4BBS project at M1, having developed the brand manual (Annex to this deliverable), deliverable and presentation's template and stationery.

4.1 Logo

As a result of the analysis of keywords which summarize themes and objectives of the project and the definition of the colour palette, the designer proposed different options for the project's logo, which can be seen in Annex 11.2.

The logo of STAR4BBS is a path starting from the **leaf**, a symbol that represents the bioeconomy, who develops on a **circle** (traceability) and ends with a movement like the symbol of **verification** (check). The central **dot** (label/certificate) draws attention, due to the positioning and colour, on the main topic of the project and closes the movement of the path.

4.2 Brand manual

After the final logo was chosen, APRE created a brand manual (Annex 11.1), which was distributed to all partners with the aim of providing them with guidelines on how to best use the logo, the specific font, colours and dimensions, as well as examples of logo applications on various materials.

4.3 Claim

The claim is a sentence that wants to enclose the main goal core of the project and catch immediately the attention of people. After analysing different alternatives, the chosen claim of STAR4BBS is *“Sustainable bio-based systems through effective certification & labelling”* .

5 Tools and channels

The achievement of the Dissemination and Communication Strategy objectives will be ensured by the complementarity of its component activities. These will ensure both project dissemination and constant and/or specific feedback from stakeholders.

APRE will manage and ensure the ongoing synergy between the activities to make the most out of the content produced within the project, by communicating the knowledge in different styles (infographics, videos, images, etc) for different platforms (website, social networks, etc). Therefore, several tools and channels will be used to support the communication of the right messages to the targeted audiences as presented below.

5.1 Website

The first version of the STAR4BBS website (splash page) was launched in December 2022 (M4) at the URL: <https://www.star4bbs.eu>. The website acts as the main portal for STAR4BBS' s editorial content, its engagement activities and all related events in which partners will participate.

All website contents will be reviewed by APRE taking into account SEO (Search Engine Optimisation) best practices for a better indexation and accessibility of the project via Internet. Additionally, the project will use Google Analytics 4 for web analytics service to track website traffic and assess useful statistics that will help to optimise the website and the communication and dissemination strategy. Relevant statistics that will be monitored are:

- Unique visitors;
- Total visitors;
- Which links and countries the web traffic comes from;
- Number of download of documents (public results, communication kit, newsletters).

The website is also the entry point for any interested user: the page 'Join our community'³ is an open form where the user can fill in with contact details for being contacted of project' s activities and results via newsletter. The policy privacy is respected as indicated in the webpage.

Structure of the website is detailed in Annex 11.3.

Table 3 shows metrics considered to reach the KPIs for this activity in the project's Grant Agreement, and the updated numbers that were accepted after the 1st review meeting in June 2024. The revision of the numbers was carried out after considering the target groups involvement in the use of the website, that is not easily engaging for the general public.

³ <https://star4bbs.eu/join-our-community/>

Table 3 Website: KPIs from Grant Agreement and adjustments from expected results

Metrics	KPIs by GA	Expected KPIs
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of visits time spent on the website and returning visitors; Number of countries; Website contents shared by visitors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> At least, 10.000 unique visitors in 3 years Visitors spending 1 minute or more on the website: >75% Website contents shared by external users on SNs: at least 400 in 3 years 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> At least, 5.000 unique visitors in 3 years Visitors spending 1 minute or more on the website: >75% Website contents shared by external users on SNs: at least 200 in 3 years

5.2 Social networks

STAR4BBS maintains an active presence in two major social media platforms: LinkedIn and Twitter. The main objective of this online presence is to reach both stakeholders and the general public thanks to a findable and recognizable production of contents. Both profiles are active since M1.

The different types of social networks used will be appropriate to reach specific target groups, and likewise the content disseminated will also depend on these groups. The same applies for paid campaigns launched for the promotion of specific initiatives or results, which will be tailored based on contents and the target audience and agreed in synergy with the Consortium.

5.2.1 Workflow

APRE set a specific workflow for SNs publications.

By the 10th of every month (to be postponed to the first working day available in case of holidays), partners can send to APRE their inputs (via the form available online on the project repository) about tasks implementation and results, but also about relevant news regarding STAR4BBS framework (activities performed, events attended, etc.). Thanks to these inputs, APRE can setup a draft of the editorial plan for the month ahead.

In addition to partners' suggestions, APRE will prepare posts about: partners' organisation and their roles in the project, short interviews to the main target stakeholders about challenges and solutions, coordinated contents with other EU projects and initiatives (e.g. EUBioNet, sisters projects, World Bio Market Insights⁴, Bioeconomy Youth Ambassadors⁵) and national target stakeholders.

8 different cards will be produced every month, to be added to other relevant publications and re-share. Once the designer has prepared the cards, the editorial

⁴ <https://worldbiomarketinsights.com/>

⁵ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/news/all-research-and-innovation-news/meet-our-bioeconomy-youth-ambassadors-2022-08-04_en

plan and the cards will be sent to the Coordinator for the final check. The Coordinator can send to APRE comments and changes by the 20th of the month.

5.2.2 LinkedIn

The LinkedIn STAR4BBS page will be used in order to increase the visibility of the project at a professional level. LinkedIn gives networking opportunity for professionals and members and creates links between different working groups and projects. LinkedIn also offers the possibility to reach many business and policy stakeholders and therefore plays a key role in the communication activities of the project.

5.2.3 Twitter

Twitter can reach a wider and more heterogeneous audience and will be used mainly for resharing and collaborations with other EU funded projects. It will be used with more frequency than other channels to post comments and news about the achievements and progress of the project and to promote project reports and participation in events.

5.2.4 YouTube

STAR4BBS YouTube account will be used as video-repository of the project, in case webinars, workshops and public co-creation activity will be recorded.

Table 4 shows metrics considered to reach the KPIs for this activity by Grant Agreement and the revised numbers that were accepted after the 1st review meeting. As for the website KPIs, social media KPIs have been updated to reflect the engagement of STAR4BBS' target audience. The project's followers are very active in interacting with what is shared on STAR4BBS' accounts, however they represent a particular sector and not the general and broader public.

Table 4 SNS: KPIs from Grant Agreement and adjustments for expected KPIs

Metrics	KPIs by GA	Expected KPIs
Number of followers, engagement rates (via SNS analytics)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> At least 2.000 followers in 3 years (considering all SNS) Twitter profile monthly visits (average): >250 by M12; >600 by M24 Monthly tweet impression (average): >10.000 by M12; >25.000 by M24 Click Through Rate (CTR) on LinkedIn (average): >5% Engagement rate on LinkedIn (average): >8% 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> At least 1.000 followers in 3 years (considering all SNS) Twitter profile monthly visits (average): >125 by M12; >300 by M24 Monthly tweet impression (average): >5.000 by M12; >12.000 by M24 Click Through Rate (CTR) on LinkedIn (average): >5% Engagement rate on LinkedIn (average): >8%

5.3 Newsletter

The consortium foresees the production of 6 newsletters during the project, whose purpose will be to raise awareness of the project and its latest news. These newsletters will be sent proactively to the target audience identified, but it will also be possible for interested parties to subscribe via the STAR4BBS website. The contacts collected throughout STAR-probio project will be used as well to disseminate STAR4BBS news, in compliance with EU Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR), thanks to the collaboration of UNITELMA, former coordinator of the project and data protector of this mailing list.

Moreover, STAR4BBS can leverage on the EuBioNet network, a proactive alliance of more than 120 EU funded projects and 17 initiatives dealing with bioeconomy promotion, communication and support, aiming to maximise the efforts, increasing the knowledge sharing, networking, mutual learning, coordination of joint activities and events. STAR4BBS joined EuBioNet since M1 and can count on its community (1458 followers on Twitter and 236 participant on LinkedIn group).

APRE, as WP7 leader, can leverage on its national network that counts on 10.950 receivers of news and events regarding Horizon Europe Cluster 6 in its database and other 3.000 receivers of *APREmagazine*, a magazine addressed to APRE members and those who are interested in the world of research and innovation.

ISEAL can share all the materials through Evidensia.eco, with more than 30.000 users among different stakeholders.

5.4 Press release

The aim of Press releases is to raise awareness and inform media and journalists about the project and main activities and results. Press releases will be sent to specific media outlets and relevant stakeholders.

Partners are encouraged to also distribute the press releases in their own languages to relevant media from their countries to ensure local dissemination.

At least four press releases will be sent to specific media outlets, and relevant stakeholders will be informed as well.

Table 5 shows metrics considered to reach the KPIs for this activity by Grant Agreement and the revised numbers, updated to reflect the engagement of the first two newsletters shared.

Table 5 Press release: KPIs from Grant Agreement and adjustments from expected KPIs

Metrics	KPIs by GA	Expected KPIs
Number of downloads; articles realised by entities external to the consortium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Press releases download: >50 Number of recipients (direct email): >300 Articles realised by media and other entities external to the consortium: >100 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Press releases download: >50 Number of recipients (direct email): >100 Articles realised by media and other entities external to the consortium: >100

5.5 Participation to relevant sectorial events

The participation in national and European/international conferences, events and fairs will allow STAR4BBS to directly liaise with key stakeholders and to provide them with constant updates on project progress. STAR4BBS partners are invited to participate in events, conferences and workshops during the project. STAR4BBS partners have already identified some relevant events where the participation of the project partners may be considered (see Table 6).

Partners are invited to give speeches, pitches, presentations and organise booths in national and international relevant events, contacting the organisers well in advance. In this way a fruitful dissemination of results will be assured.

Table 6 A selection of relevant European events

Title	When	Type of event
ECOMONDO	November 2023	Conference/ Exhibition
EUBCE - European Biomass Conference & Exhibition	June 2023	Conference/ Exhibition
EFIB - European Forum for Industrial Biotechnology	October 2023	Conference/ Networking event
Global Bioeconomy Summit	TBD	Conference/ Exhibition
CBE JU Stakeholder Forum	<u>December 2023</u>	Conference/ Networking event
ERSCP - European Roundtable for Sustainable Consumption and Production	July 2023	Conference
CBE JU Info Day and networking event	TBD	Conference/ Networking event
ESDW - European Sustainable Development Week	TBD	Conference/ Exhibition
EU Green Week	June 2023 (annual event)	Conference/ Exhibition
ESOF – Euro Science Open Forum	2024 edition (biannual event)	Conference
International Bioeconomy conference	June 2023	Conference

Table 7 shows metrics considered to reach the KPIs for this activity.

Table 7 Participation to events: KPIs from Grant Agreement

Metrics	KPI
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Numbers of events • Number of attendees 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of people reached during the events: >7.500

5.6 Online webinars

Training online courses (including related materials that will be developed jointly with all the partners) will aim to disseminate STAR4BBS outputs to relevant stakeholders. Organized by UNI, the English version of the training will be recorded and made available on the website, jointly with the training materials, that will be translated in 6 languages.

Project partners will be empowered on the training contents, and they will be responsible for the organization of at least 3 training online courses aimed at different stakeholders, in particular the business community, in their countries.

6 Tools and channels per target group

The following Table 8 showcases how each STAR4BBS target group will be approached and with which tool and by which channel.

Table 8 Tools and channels per main target

Tools and channels	Target groups						
	Standards setting, labelling and certification organisations (even certification bodies)	Academia, research institutions and researchers	Value chains actors	EU Policymakers	Intergovernmental organizations	Civil society, organizations and end-consumers	EU funded projects
Website	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Webinars	X	X	X	X	X		X
Communication kit (flyer, poster, rollups)	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Social networks		X	X	X	X	X	X
Press release/media presence	X		X	X	X		X
Newsletter	X	X		X	X		X
Videos	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Conferences	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

7 STAR4BBS Key Performance indicators

7.1 KPIs as a tool to monitor and evaluate progress

The KPIs proposed for STAR4BBS are calculated taking into account the sector and topic in which the project operates in, and are tailored to highlight its growth potential. The STAR4BBS Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are therefore important as a reference during the monitoring and evaluation activities to trace progress of the Communication and Dissemination Strategy throughout the project implementation.

KPIs are based on estimates of the engagement rates that communication and dissemination activities can generate both online (through website and social media) and offline (events participation).

APRE is responsible for the evaluation of the KPIs: every two months, using ad hoc monitoring tools (social media platforms built-in analytics and Matomo for the STAR4BBS website), the metric data are collected and compared with the previous numbers, to understand the project's online presence evolution.

If necessary, this monitoring process allows to adapt the Communication and Dissemination strategy according to emerging challenges or to use new successful formats. The monitoring of the KPIs is helpful in terms of engaging relevant stakeholders, for example by using the built-in LinkedIn function that identifies the job sector of STAR4BBS profile's followers.

At the end of the implementation activities, the collection of the KPIs by the monitoring activities will give a precise path that demonstrates STAR4BBS' progress towards WP7's objectives, and will show the increasing numbers in terms of higher followers count and engagement rates (i.e.: more interactions with posts and website contents).

7.2 KPIs expected

A Performance indicator represents what the successful outcome should be in terms of impact on the economy/society beyond those directly affected by the project activities⁶.

A set of KPIs are defined in the Grant Agreement in order to assess the implementation of the Strategy every 12 months. KPIs will enable APRE to correct and adapt the strategy (through a dedicated section within periodic report at M18), considering also new emerging needs or external factors affecting the project. KPIs are built considering ones contained in the Grant Agreement and new ones introduced in the first months of the project.

In the yearly assessment, the following Table 9 will be updated with a column showing the progresses.

⁶ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *Horizon 2020 indicators: assessing the results and impact of Horizon*, Publications Office, 2015, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/71098>

Table 9 Expected outputs, KPIs by Grant Agreement and adjustments from expected result

Tools, activities, channels	Metrics	KPIs by GA	Expected results
Website	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of visits, time spent on the website and returning visitors; Number of countries; Website contents shared by visitors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> At least, 10.000 unique visitors in 3 years Visitors spending 1 minute or more on the website: >75% Website contents shared by external users on SNs: at least 400 in 3 years 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> At least, 5.000 unique visitors in 3 years Visitors spending 1 minute or more on the website: >75% Website contents shared by external users on SNs: at least 200 in 3 years
Press release	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of downloads; articles realised by entities external to the consortium 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Press releases download: >50 Number of recipients (direct email): >300 Articles realised by media and other entities external to the consortium: >100 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Press releases download: >50 Number of recipients (direct email): >100 Articles realised by media and other entities external to the consortium: >100
Social Networks (SNs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of followers, engagement rates (via SNs analytics) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> At least 2.000 followers in 3 years (considering all SNs) Twitter profile monthly visits (average): 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> At least 1.000 followers in 3 years (considering all SNs) Twitter profile monthly visits (average): >125 by M12; >300 by M24

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >250 by M12; >600 by M24 • Monthly tweet impression (average): >10.000 by M12; >25.000 by M24 • Click Through Rate (CTR) on LinkedIn (average): >5% • Engagement rate on LinkedIn (average): >8% 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monthly tweet impression (average): >5.000 by M12; >12.000 by M24 • Click Through Rate (CTR) on LinkedIn (average): >5% • Engagement rate on LinkedIn (average): >8%
<p>Events and conferences</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Numbers of events, number of attendees 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of people reached during the events: >7.500 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of people reached during the events: >7.500

Beside the Metrics methodology and target KPIs identified in accordance with the specific activity performed in the frame of STAR4BBS, a general approach has been identified in order to fulfil the project objectives.

7.3 Online engagement indicators

- Delivery Rate = number of emails delivered/number of emails sent (measured in percentage);
- Open Rate = number of emails opened/number of emails delivered (measured in percentage);
- Opt-out Rate = number of unsubscribers/number of emails opened (measured in percentage);
- Click to delivery rate = number of clicks in the email/number of emails delivered (measured in percentage);
- Response Rate = Total number of first time responses/total number of emails opened.

7.4 SNs and website engagement indicators

In the table below, a list of the tools and, what they are applied for, that are used to collect and analyze data needed to monitor the KPIs during the implementation of communication and dissemination activities.

These tools allow APRE and the Partners to understand the impact of communication and dissemination activities, in particular the ones related to social media platforms and STAR4BBS' website. The tools mentioned below assist in measuring target audiences' engagement in relation to content published, and are GDPR compliant.

Table 10 metrics and analytics for SNs and STAR4BBS website

TOOLS	DATA
Google Analytics 4 by GA, substituted by Matomo in implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unique visitors on the project website • Total visits on the project website
LinkedIn statistics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LinkedIn followers
Twitter Analytics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Twitter impressions • New followers, Nr. Tweets, Impressions, Link clicks, Retweets, Favourites, Replies, Mention
YouTube counter	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • YouTube views

7.5 Offline engagement Indicators

Quantitative Analysis

- Quantity and quality of submissions/participations;
- Former engaged stakeholder vs. novel engaged stakeholder

Qualitative Analysis

- Stakeholder satisfaction
- Community Building, in terms of established collaborations (link also to T7.3)
- Awareness raising, in terms of STAR4BBS SNs subscribers after the event
- Cost effectiveness, in terms of effort used compared to the above-mentioned indicators
- Performance improvements

7.6 Barriers and obstacles to reach KPIs

The potential barriers to dissemination and communication related to the main actions foreseen are identified in Table 11.

Table 11 Barriers and obstacles to reach KPIs

Tools, activities, channels	Metrics	Barriers and obstacles
Website	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of visits, time spent on the website and returning visitors; • Number of countries; website contents shared by visitors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Partners do not promote in their channels the website • Other EU projects and initiatives do not reshare news and contents through their channels • Limited number of information sources trusted/preferred
Press release	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of downloads • Articles realised by entities external to the consortium 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low confidence in the quality of the information provided • Unclear utility and relevance for users • Non-user-friendly format
Social Networks (SNs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of followers, engagement rates (via SNs analytics) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited capacity to reach intended users • Project results presented in language not adapted and/or not accessible to the different target groups • Limited attractiveness of the information
Events and conferences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Numbers of events • Number of attendees 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Too many events focused on similar contents • Restriction to the participation on on-site events • Participants do not see added value of the event

These barriers could be overcome by a clear definition of the target groups that STAR4BBS wants to reach and engage, defining the content in a way that is really attractive to them. Additionally, the management structure developed for the involvement of all partners in the process of dissemination and communication activities should assure the achievement of the KPIs.

8 Communication and dissemination management structure

8.1 CoDNOC

During the Kick-off meeting held in Berlin, Serena Fabbrini (APRE) was appointed as the Communication, Dissemination, Networking and Outreach Coordinator (CoDNOC) for STAR4BBS. Responsibilities of the CoDNOC include the supervision of the formulation of the Communication and Dissemination Strategy, as well as the creation of a brand identity including the STAR4BBS logo and templates for website, dissemination and training documents and presentations. During the first months of the project, the CoDNOC has ensured that all resources (e.g. website, flyers, posters, presentation slides and promotional banners) have a professional and uniform look, aligned with the visual identity of the project. The activities CoDNOC covers:

1. Coordination, organisation and monitoring of all dissemination activities;
2. Encouraging partners to initiate and to participate;
3. Ensuring regular quality content for the various dissemination channels and activities.

The CoDNOC, along with her team, will have the final check to ensure all materials produced by major activities are aligned with the visuals of the project, before their external distribution takes place

8.2 Partners' Responsibilities

APRE, leader of the WP7, is responsible for the overall management and support of the activities defined under the present dissemination and communication strategy; moreover, it is in charge for the development of the main tools and graphic materials that will be used during the project.

Each partner will:

- Contribute to the communication and dissemination strategy implementation;
- Engage new stakeholders in their hub and animate the cooperation with them;
- Ensure the control of the quality of the activities implemented.

All STAR4BBS partners will be actively involved in the implementation of communication and dissemination activities. More specifically, the expected contributions from partners are the following:

- Implementing dissemination activities in their own countries and at European level;
- Exploiting their contacts, networks and channels;
- Supplying news and updates for the web portal and newsletter via the form available on the project repository;
- Helping to keep the project's Social Media Accounts (SMAs) alive and active, in particular supporting the development of contents to be communicated;
- Participating to conferences, workshops, events etc. in order to promote the project and its outcomes.

8.2.1 Communication Referee

In order to facilitate communication and meetings between APRE and each partner regarding communication activities, each partner should appoint a Communication Referee. The Referee will liaise with APRE to evaluate monthly via an online meeting the activities implemented and organize new ones (both onsite and online). APRE, responsible of all the tasks under the Communication and Dissemination activities, will coordinate all the meetings with the Referee and will report to the Coordinator of STAR4BBS.

8.3 Procedures and reporting

Monitoring will be carried out by each partner on a regular basis through an online report template uploaded on the TubCloud.

The communication and dissemination strategy will undergo a periodic update, every 12 months. Through continuous monitoring, STAR4BBS will be able to continuously measure its performance, key impacts and propose corrective actions to improve performance and maximise impacts, if needed, thus adopting a fully scalable approach to its Communication and Dissemination strategy.

Measurement of impacts and outreach will be guaranteed by the consolidated monitoring report, involving both the online, social media channels and the engagement activities as described in the Technical Annex to the Grant Agreement.

To measure the engagement and interest via off-line communication, feedback will be collected from the participants in STAR4BBS workshops and events. The partners will collect qualitative feedback via questionnaires shared after (or during) the event itself (see Annex 11.4). The integration of outreach data, online engagement and qualitative stakeholders' feedback will constitute the basis for an integrated analysis of the impacts generated by the project activities.

The monitoring activity will be carried out on a regular basis and its first outcomes will be included in the periodic report (M18). The periodic report will also contain a section dedicated to the updated information of this Strategy, if any.

In order to guarantee the effective involvement of all partners in the communication and dissemination activities, procedures concerning reporting activities and for contributing to the activities were defined.

An online spreadsheet (see Annex 11.5) was created in order to track all the communication and dissemination activities performed by partners. It contains two different sheets, one for communication activities and one for dissemination ones. In depth, each sheet contains (Table 12):

Table 12 Dissemination and communication requested fields

Dissemination activities	Communication activities
Partner	Partner
WP	WP
Dissemination activity name	Communication activity name
Type of activity	Type of activity
Target audience	Description
Date	Target audience
Description of objectives with reference to specific project output	Communication channel
Link/website	Date
Status of the activity	Outcome (KPIs)
# of people reached	Status of the activity
	Link/website
	# of people reached

9 Timeline

In this chapter, a timeline for all WP7 related activities expected to be implemented throughout STAR4BBS project is provided. A disclaimer is needed: as mentioned in previous chapters, monitoring activity will be carried out on a regular basis and its first outcomes will be included in the periodic report (M18). The periodic report will also contain a section dedicated to the updated information of this Strategy, if any.

All the KPIs reported in this table refers to the GA (WP7 and Section 2.2).

Table 13 Timeline of the main releases related to Communication and Dissemination activities

YEAR 1	
M	Activities
M1	Logo, ppt template, launch of SNS
M2	Definition of website pages, creation of STAR4BBS Brand identity
M3	Poster #1 (contents with TUB), definition of website pages (II)
M4	STAR4BBS splash page, delivery of Poster #1, definition of website pages (III), Word Template for deliverables
M5	STAR4BBS website online
M6	STAR4BBS Strategy for dissemination, exploitation and communication (D7.1) with Communication Kit (stationery and promotional materials)
M7	
M8	Newsletter #1
M9	
M10	Press release #1
M11	Infographic #1
M12	
YEAR 2	
M13	Newsletter #2, Promotional video #1
M14	Infographic #2
M15	
M16	Press release #2
M17	Infographic #3
M18	
M19	Newsletter #3

M20

M21 Infographic #4

M22

M23

M24

YEAR 3

M25 Newsletter #4, video #2, Infographic #5

M26

M27

M28 Press release #3, Infographic #6

M29

M30 Newsletter #5

M31 Infographic #7

M32

M33 Infographic #8

M34

M35 Newsletter #6, Infographic #9

M36 Press release #4, Infographic #10

10 Exploitation of the results

An efficient exploitation of results is a key premise for enhancing the project's outcomes and impacts after its end.

The project's multilanguage website will be available for at least three years after the project end, providing among others selected project data and accessing and downloading of all public deliverables.

As one of the main project's goals is to increase the robustness and effectiveness of SCS and labels related to bio-based feedstocks, materials and products, from month 14, UNITELMA will start gaining inputs from all partners in order to define approaches and procedures to further adopt and replicate the monitoring system developed through the project. It is expected that during the project duration the process for creating a fast-track standard around the monitoring system will be started, with the support of UNI. This activity will be coordinated with sister projects to avoid any duplication of effort and fatigue of the stakeholders.

In addition the monitoring system and other relevant results will be disseminated through Evidensia.eco, managed by ISEAL, that has more than 30.000 users among different stakeholders including businesses.

Key exploitable results such as, among others, the examination of trade flows regarding biological feedstock and bio-based materials and products and the analysis of indicators covering environmental, social, economic and circular aspects will be disseminated through recommendations, policy papers/reports (grey literature), and peer-reviewed scientific publications that will be communicated also through posters at international meetings and conferences.

Regarding peer-reviewed publications, a minimum of 8 articles will be published in high-impact factor journals and will be freely available in the form of open access publications.

All STAR4BBS partners are committed to ensure open access to their peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to project results. These requirements include depositing a copy of the final peer-reviewed manuscript in a trusted repository for scientific publications, providing immediate open access to the deposited publication, and providing information about any research output or tools necessary to validate the publication's conclusions. The metadata of deposited publications must also be openly available (only publication fees for fully open access venues are eligible for reimbursement. Beneficiaries must retain sufficient intellectual property rights to meet open access requirements).

For long term archive, the 8 publications will be available on STAR4BBS Zenodo Community, that is reachable at the following address: <https://zenodo.org/communities/star4bbs/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>.

In addition, exploitation activities will be also compliant with the Data Management Plan (DMP) (D8.2).

11 Annexes

11.1 Brand manual

visual identity color palette

COLOR	PRIMARY MEANING	SECONDARY MEANING
<p>#49BB70</p>	<p>bio products knowledge</p>	<p>welfare hygiene</p>
<p>#008C96</p>	<p>credibility seriousness</p>	<p>truth order</p>
<p>#E39100</p>	<p>confidence optimism</p>	<p>open air happiness</p>
<p>NEUTRAL</p> <p>#C0C0C0</p>	<p>It's a good base for the palette: due to its neutrality, lends itself to being combined with almost all colors.</p>	

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project key words

KEY WORDS

- certification
- labels
- traceability
- bioeconomy

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11.2 Logo

logo concept

This logo proposal is basically a path starting from the leaf, a symbol that represents the bioeconomy, who develops on a circle (traceability) and ends with a movement similar to the symbol of verification (check). The central dot (label / certificate) draws attention, due to the positioning and color, on the main topic of the project and closes the movement of the path.

logo anatomy

STAR4BBS logo is a combination mark :

Pictogram (Logo Mark) + Wordmark + Payoff

Each part of the logo can be used alone or composed, in this way there is great flexibility for different applications.

Pictogram or Logo Mark

Payoff

(if you want to include the pay off this is the right position)

Wordmark

logo versions - official colors - white background

logo versions - official color - dark background

logo dimension & propositions - safety area

Safety area ensures that external elements are not interfering in the mark readability. It should be always respected this margin corresponding to the height of the character "S".

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logo dimension & propositions - minimum size

Minimum dimensions to ensure the readability of the mark.

Printed media:

The minimum size for the logo is 35mm width for the official version or 25 mm width for the vertical version. For sizes below this measures only the pictogram, up to 10 mm, must be used. Below 10mm must be used just the wordmark.

Digital formats:

The minimum size for the logo is 220 px width for the official version or 120 px width for the vertical version. For sizes below this measures only the pictogram, up to 60 px, must be used. Below 60 px must be used just the wordmark.

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selected fonts

MAIN FONT

Raleway font family

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrst
 uvwxyz
 1234567890
 ?!"#\$%&'()*+,-./:;<=>?
 @!\$%&'()*+,-./:;<=>?
 @!\$%&'()*+,-./:;<=>?

For this project are used two fonts:

- Raleway font Family for titles
- Montserrat font Family for sub-titles and plain text

Raleway - bold

LOREM IPSUM

dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.

Montserrat - regular

Raleway - bold

LOREM IPSUM

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Ut enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exercitation ullamco laboris nisi ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat

Montserrat - regular

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11.3 Website and SNs

Fig. 1 Website tree

Fig. 2 Website homepage

Fig. 3 Website: workflow

Work Plan and Resources

Fig. 4 Website: WPs links

Fig. 5 Website: subscribe to the newsletter

Fig. 6 Website: subscribe to STAR4BBS Database

Fig. 7 STAR4BBS LinkedIn account homepage

Fig. 8 STAR4BBS Twitter account homepage

11.4 Feedback questionnaire

FEEDBACK QUESTIONNAIRE

Name of event
dd-mm-yyyy

Partners:

www.star4bbs.eu
info@star4bbs.eu
@STAR4BBS

Powered by

FEEDBACK QUESTIONNAIRE

Name of the event: xxx xxx xxx
Venue: xxx xxx xxx
Date: xx / xx / xxxx

Your NAME: xxx xxx xxx
Your ORGANIZATION: xxx xxx xxx
Your POSITION: xxx xxx xxx
Your EMAIL: xxx xxx xxx

Which stakeholder group do you belong to? *(tick more than one if applicable)*

- Certification schemes owners
- Academia / Research organization
- Association (consumers, employees' organization)
- Policymaker / Public institution
- NGO
- Industry
- Civil Society
- Other *please specify* _____

www.star4bbs.eu @STAR4BBS
info@star4bbs.eu

INSTRUCTIONS

Please answer all questions as fully as you can and add comments in the free space as appropriate.

Where a numerical rating is requested, please rate aspects of your experience of the STAR4BBS event on a 1 to 5 scale as explained below:

1 = "Strongly disagree," or the lowest, most negative impression
3 = "Neither agree nor disagree," or an adequate impression
5 = "Strongly agree," or the highest, most positive impression

Choose or state N/A if the item is not appropriate for you or not applicable to the event you attended.

www.star4bbs.eu @STAR4BBS
info@star4bbs.eu

1 Summary

	1	2	3	4	5	N/A
Overall quality of the event	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Efficacy of STAR4BBS facilitation team	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Value of information available/presented	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Value of discussions & interaction	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Usefulness of STAR4BBS event for you/your organisation	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Venue & Logistics	<input type="checkbox"/>					

Please use this space for any further overall comments.

2. What content / views did you hear / learn about at the event that contribute to the views of your organisation and you? Contribute as many answers that are appropriate

- 2.1 Common challenges
- 2.2 Policy/public sector landscape
- 2.3 Industry
- 2.4 Research
- 2.5 Civil society
- 2.6 Successful solutions
- 2.7 Other

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3 What connections did you make at the event of interest to you/your organisation & why are they of interest?

- 3.1 from industry
- 3.2 from Policy/public sector
- 3.3 from Research
- 3.4 from Civil Society
- 3.5 Other

4 What follow-up are you considering / or planning post the event?

- 4.1 Arranging meetings (with whom/why)
- 4.2 Further information gathering (on what/why)
- 4.3 Review of your organisation's content/document (what/why)
- 4.4 Other

5 Do you have any suggestions as to how future STAR4BBS event could be more effective?

- 5.1 Agenda / focus?
- 5.2 Participants?
- 5.3 Information?
- 5.4 Follow-up?
- 5.5 Other

www.star4bbs.eu @STAR4BBS
info@star4bbs.eu

Please use this space for your free comments on overall value of interest in similar events/follow-up

Thank you very much indeed for taking the time to complete this feedback form.

www.star4bbs.eu @STAR4BBS
info@star4bbs.eu

11.5 Monitoring files

The public disclosure of the results by appropriate means, other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results, including by scientific publications in any medium.

PARTNER	WP	Task	Dissemination activity name	TYPE OF ACTIVITY	TARGET AUDIENCE	Why? Description of objectives with reference to specific project output (max. 200 characters)	RELATE WEBSITE/LINK	Status of the activity	# OF PEOPLE REACHED

Fig. 9 Dissemination sheet

Communication measures should promote the project throughout the full lifespan of the project. The aim is to inform and reach out to society and show the activities performed, and the use and the benefits the project will have for citizens.

PARTNER	WP	TASK	Communication activity name (short label as described in communication, dissemination and exploitation plan)	TYPE OF ACTIVITY	DESCRIPTION	TARGET audience	How? Communication channel	Outcome (specific key performance indicators)	Status of the activity	RELATE WEBSITE/LINK	# OF PEOPLE REACHED

Fig. 10 Communication sheet

STAR4BBS | News & Communication materials ongoing collection

Dear Partners,
you are asked to fill this form, in order to ease the collection of the news to be published in the different project's channels communication.

Your organisation organises an interesting webinar? Fill the form, we'll promote it!
Your project published a study interesting for the community or is launching a call/survey? Fill the form!
You are a WP leader and you have a new result to promote? Fill the form!

Please, remember: if you want to add any images to complete the news, send it/them via email to star4bbs@apre.it or put it/them in a link for the download.

Thank you!
APRE team

* Obbligatoria

1. Your organization *

2. Title/topic *

3. Text (Please, provide a short text that we can adapt and re-use (300 characters, including spaces) *

4. Do you want to suggest who to tag in the post? And any hashtag? *

5. Where do you suggest to publish? *

Social media
 Website
 Newsletter
 Altro

6. Date *

Immetti la data (dd/MM/yyyy)

7. Do you want to provide any additional information?

Fig. 11 News & Communication materials ongoing collection

11.6 Stationery and promotional materials: the Communication Kit

11.6.1 Deliverable template

The image displays a grid of 12 pages from the Star4bbs Deliverable template. The pages are arranged in three rows and four columns. Each page features the Star4bbs logo in the top left corner and a decorative pattern on the right side. The pages include the following sections:

- Page 1:** 'Number of Deliverable' section with a large white circle containing the text 'Num. of Deliverable Deliverable Title here (may have three or four lines)'. It also lists partner logos (TU, UWI, USU, APRE, BAM, RSB, Total) and contact information (www.star4bbs.eu, info@star4bbs.eu, @STAR4BBS).
- Page 2:** 'Number of Deliverable' section with a form for 'DELIVERABLE TYPE', 'LEADER', 'WORK PACKAGE', 'CONTRIBUTOR LEVEL', and 'SUBJECT'. It includes a table for 'Programme', 'Grant', 'Start', and 'Duration'.
- Page 3:** 'Contributors' section with a table for 'NAME' and 'ORGANISATION'. It also includes 'Peer Reviews' and 'Revision History' tables.
- Page 4:** 'Index of Contents' section with a table listing sections and page numbers.
- Page 5:** 'Partners short names' section with a table for 'TYPE', 'UNIT/TEAM', 'LSC', 'LSC', 'APRE', 'USU', 'BAM', 'RSB', and 'TOTAL'.
- Page 6:** 'Executive summary' section with a heading and a note: 'Here you write the executive summary (up to 1/3 page)'.
- Page 7:** 'Landscape' section with a heading and a table for 'YEAR'.
- Page 8:** 'Landscape' section with a heading and a table for 'YEAR'.
- Page 9:** 'Landscape' section with a heading and a table for 'YEAR'.
- Page 10:** 'Landscape' section with a heading and a table for 'YEAR'.
- Page 11:** 'Landscape' section with a heading and a table for 'YEAR'.
- Page 12:** 'Landscape' section with a heading and a table for 'YEAR'.

11.6.2 PowerPoint template

 EDIT KICKER

Fare clic sull'icona per inserire un'immagine

Fare clic sull'icona per inserire un'immagine

 Funded by the European Union

 EDIT KICKER

Fare clic sull'icona per inserire un'immagine

title

Fare clic per inserire testo

 Funded by the European Union

<i>name of presenter</i>
<i>organization</i>
<i>email</i>
<i>phone</i>
<i>relevant details</i>

Thank you for your attention!

11.6.3 Flyer

What STAR4BBS does:

The overall aim of STAR4BBS is to maximize the potential of Sustainability Certification Schemes (SCS) and labels to support a successful transition to sustainable bio-based economy.

STAR4BBS will develop indicators and a new monitoring system for assessing the effectiveness and robustness of existing international and EU SCS, B2B labels, and related traceability systems applicable to biological feedstock and bio-based materials and products. Thus creating the foundations to support achieving the harmonization between schemes and transparency in global and EU trade flows.

Who we are

Partners of STAR4BBS have strong experience in developing and applying sustainable standards, indicators and monitoring system, in tracing flows of biological feedstocks and bio-based materials and products and in assessing the costs of adopting SCS and labels. The consortium includes partners from academic institutions, private research institutes, non-profit associations and well established institutions.

Who we work with

Project involves important stakeholders, including scheme owners, policy makers, and industries. They are involved in the design of research and the monitoring system and also in the development of practical recommendations emerging from the research and analysis, to ensure STAR4BBS ultimate goal.

JOIN OUR COMMUNITY!

11.6.4 Rollup

 Star4bbs

“ Sustainable bio-based systems through effective certification & labelling ”

Join Us !

www.star4bbs.eu
@STAR4BBS

Consortium

 Funded by the European Union

11.6.5 Agenda template

The agenda template is presented in three formats: a vertical poster, a horizontal flyer, and a table.

Vertical Poster: Features the Star4bbs logo at the top, followed by the agenda title, subtitle, and copy. It includes a date, a live/online status, a list of partners, and contact information (website, email, social media).

Horizontal Flyer: Similar to the poster, it includes the Star4bbs logo, agenda title, subtitle, copy, date, live/online status, partners, and contact information.

Table: A table with three columns: TIME, TITLE, and SPEAKER. It lists various time slots and corresponding speakers.

TIME	TITLE	SPEAKER
09:00 - 10:00	Lorem Ipsum	Name Surname, Institution
10:00 - 11:00	Lorem Ipsum	Name Surname, Institution
11:00 - 12:00	Lorem Ipsum	Name Surname, Institution
12:00 - 13:00	Lorem Ipsum	Name Surname, Institution
	BREAK	
14:00 - 15:00	Lorem Ipsum	Name Surname, Institution
15:00 - 16:00	Lorem Ipsum	Name Surname, Institution
16:00 - 17:00	Lorem Ipsum	Name Surname, Institution

11.6.6 Virtual background

“ Sustainable bio-based systems via effective certification & labelling ”

Consortium:

Unitelma Sapienza
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